

CHALLENGES AND POTENTIAL OF MULTIMODE OPTICAL FIBERS AS RAMAN PROBE SENSORS FOR NAD AND RHODAMINE 6G DETECTION

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Abstract – This study explores the application of optical fibers as Raman probe-type sensors for the detection of NAD (Nicotinamide Adenine Dinucleotide) and R6G (Rhodamine 6G) molecules. NAD is crucial in biological systems, participating in redox reactions essential for cellular energy production. Rhodamine 6G, in turn, is a fluorescent dye widely used in Raman spectroscopy due to its intense Raman scattering. Initially, fibers with deposited test molecules were analyzed using a Raman spectrometer, focusing the laser on the cross-section opposite to the one with the test molecule. Subsequently, the fibers were repositioned with the laser directly focused on the cross-section with the deposited test molecule. The study demonstrates the potential of optical fibers as Raman sensors, highlighting challenges and opportunities in the development of advanced biosensors.

Keywords: Raman Spectroscopy; Nicotinamide Adenine Dinucleotide (NAD); Rhodamine 6G; Biosensor; Optical Fiber Probe.

INTRODUCTION

The NAD (Nicotinamide Adenine Dinucleotide) molecule is essential in biological systems, participating in vital redox reactions for cellular energy production and metabolism maintenance [1]. Its detection and quantification are crucial for biochemical and clinical studies [2]. On the other hand, Rhodamine 6G is a fluorescent dye widely used in Raman spectroscopy due to its intense Raman scattering, facilitating the identification of its spectral features [3]. Figure 1 illustrates the structures of NAD and Rhodamine 6G.

Figure 1 - Molecular structures of NAD (a) and Rhodamine 6G (b). [4-5].

Raman spectroscopy, which provides a spectrum considered the "fingerprint" of a molecule, is a powerful technique for detailed molecular analysis. The application of optical fibers as Raman probes for the detection of molecules in biosensors offers an innovative approach for the remote and sensitive detection of biomolecules [6]. Probe-type biosensors are particularly advantageous in *in vivo* analyses, where minimally invasive techniques are desired. Optical fibers can serve as a medium for transporting Raman signals, enabling the analysis of biomolecules.

This study investigates the effectiveness of optical fibers as Raman probes for the detection of NAD and Rhodamine 6G, highlighting the challenges faced and the potential of this technology in enhancing advanced biosensors.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The β -NAD (beta Nicotinamide Adenine Dinucleotide) and Rhodamine 6G molecules were provided in powder form by Sigma-Aldrich®. The solutions were prepared using a Simplicity Merck Millipore® ultrapure water system and a Marte AU@220D® precision balance. A Renishaw InVia-2000® Raman spectrometer was used to collect the sample spectra, with an excitation laser of $\lambda = 785$ nm and a 50x objective lens with a numerical aperture (N.A.) of 0.75. At the beginning of each experiment, the Raman spectrometer was properly calibrated using a silicon wafer as a reference, based on the silicon optical phonon at 520 cm^{-1} . This characteristic Raman line results from the vibration of silicon atoms in the crystal. Sample preparation followed the methods adopted in [7].

The NAD molecule was diluted to a concentration of 10^{-3} mol/L in an aqueous solution containing 0.1 mol/L of KCl using the well-known equation (1).

$$m = C \times M_m \times V \quad (1)$$

Where,

m - Mass of solute, g;

C - Desired concentration, mol/L;

M_m - Molar mass of solute, g/mol;

V - Volume of solution, L.

Segments of multimode fiber with a fused silica core with diameter of 1 mm were used as the substrate for the deposition of the test molecules. These fibers were supplied by New Port Company®.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The optical fibers were cleaved, and the cross-sections were carefully polished (Figure 2). The cross-sectional areas were degreased with acetone at $55 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 90 minutes, followed by immersion in a container with preheated isopropanol at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10

minutes. Subsequently, the cross-sections were dried using a N₂ jet.

Figure 2 - Microscope image of the multimode optical fiber cross-section after cleaving and polishing, showing lateral view (a) and frontal view (b). In both figures, the scale bar corresponds to 500 µm.

After the degreasing process, the cross-section of one fiber segment was immersed in the NAD solution, while another segment was immersed in the Rhodamine 6G solution, with both remaining submerged for 24 hours. Then, the fibers were removed from their respective solutions, and the sections were dried using a N₂ jet. As a result, only a thin layer of test molecules remained adsorbed on the cross-sectional areas of the core.

The fibers with deposited test molecules were taken to the Raman spectrometer. To evaluate the application of the fiber as a probe-type sensor, the objective initially focused the laser on the cross-section opposite to the one where the NAD molecule had been deposited. The goal was to excite the fiber with the laser at one end to obtain the Raman spectrum of the molecule deposited at the other end. Spectra were obtained at powers of 70 µW, 7 mW, 35 mW, and 70 mW, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Raman spectra at different excitation powers with the laser focused on the end opposite to the deposited molecules.

The peaks around 490 cm⁻¹ and 611 cm⁻¹ are known as D1 and D2 lines and are attributed to four- and three-membered rings, respectively [8-9]. The band around 810 cm⁻¹ is related to bending modes of the Si-O-Si bond. Hass, M. proposed that the band at 1061 cm⁻¹ be attributed to a stretching vibration of a chemical bond [10]. This spectral profile corresponds to the fused silica core, and above the noise level, there are no lines related to NAD. The Raman spectrum of the fiber with deposited Rhodamine 6G showed a similar profile. These results indicate that the application of optical fiber as a Raman probe-type

sensor for NAD and Rhodamine 6G remains challenging.

Subsequently, the optical fiber segment with deposited NAD was repositioned in the Raman spectrometer so that the objective lens directly focused the laser on the cross-sectional area with the deposited test molecule. The resulting spectrum is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Raman spectra of NAD deposited on the optical fiber cross-section.

Note that this time, the Raman lines of NAD appear in the spectrum between 1250 cm⁻¹ and 1700 cm⁻¹. The line at 1285 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the adenine ring [11]. The line at 1420 cm⁻¹ represents a 50% contribution from the adenine ring with a small influence from ribose, and 50% from the nicotinamide group [11-12]. The line at 1610 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the nicotinamide ring [11 and 13]. When comparing the spectra from Figures 3 and 4, it is evident that these lines do not correspond to the fiber core but rather to the NAD molecule.

The optical fiber segment with the Rhodamine 6G molecule was also repositioned in the Raman spectrometer so that the objective focused the laser directly on the cross-sectional area with the deposited Rhodamine (Figure 5).

The presence of lines attributed to Rhodamine 6G can be observed in the range between 600 cm⁻¹ and 1700 cm⁻¹. The intense lines between 1314 cm⁻¹ and 1651 cm⁻¹ are attributed to a stretching vibration of the aromatic C-C bond. The line at 774 cm⁻¹ corresponds to a bending mode vibration of the C-H bond, and the line at 614 cm⁻¹ is attributed to C-C-C bending [14].

Optical fibers with gold nanocylinders on the cross-sectional area, fabricated in previous works, were also tested to enhance Raman scattering, but no significant enhancement was observed for these molecules [7]. Further experiments are underway to investigate other nanostructure geometries capable of enhancing Raman scattering in samples with optical fiber substrates.

Figura 5 - Espectros Raman de R6G depositada na secção da fibra óptica.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results obtained, the application of optical fibers as Raman probe-type sensors for the detection of molecules such as NAD and Rhodamine 6G proved to be challenging. When the laser was focused on the cross-section opposite to the one with the deposited test molecules, the resulting Raman spectrum was dominated by the characteristics of the fiber's silica matrix, without showing lines related to the test molecules above the noise level. This suggests that excitation from one end of the fiber was not effective in detecting the molecules at the other end due to interference from the silica core. A possible solution would be to study new fiber materials with low Raman scattering in the spectral range of the test molecule's scattering.

However, when the fiber was repositioned so that the laser was focused directly on the cross-section with the deposited test molecules, the Raman characteristics of the NAD and Rhodamine 6G molecules were clearly detectable. The specific Raman lines for NAD and Rhodamine 6G, located between 1250 cm^{-1} and 1700 cm^{-1} , were observed, confirming the presence of the molecules in the fiber. These results indicate that, although remote detection through the fiber as a waveguide is challenging, the technique may be feasible with the application of nanoparticles that enhance the Raman scattering of these molecules, suggesting a promising path for the development of optical fiber-based Raman sensors.

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